

Single-Criteria Metric r -Dominating Set Problem via Minor-Preserving Support

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1 — Abstract —

2 Given an unweighted graph G , the *minimum r -dominating set problem* asks for a subset of vertices
 3 S of the smallest cardinality, such that every vertex in G is within radius r to some vertex in S .
 4 While the r -dominating set problem on planar graph admits PTAS from Baker's shifting/layering
 5 technique when r is a constant, the problem becomes significantly harder when r can depend on
 6 n . In fact, under Exponential-Time Hypothesis, Fox-Epstein *et al.* [SODA 2019] observed that no
 7 efficient PTAS can exist for the unbounded r -dominating set problem on planar graphs. One may
 8 consider even harder weighted-variant known as the *vertex-weighted metric r -dominating set*, where
 9 edges are associated with lengths, and every vertex is associated with a positive-valued weight, and
 10 the goal is to compute an r -dominating set with minimum total weight. As a result, people resorted
 11 to *bicriteria* algorithms by allowing the returned solution to use radius- $(1 + \epsilon)r$ balls instead, in
 12 addition to the total weight being a $1 + \epsilon$ approximation to the optimal value.

13 We establish the first *single-criteria* polynomial-time $O(1)$ -approximation algorithm for the
 14 vertex-weighted metric r -dominating set problem on planar graphs when r is part of the input, and
 15 can be arbitrarily large compared to n . Our new (single-criteria) $O(1)$ -approximation algorithm
 16 uses the quasi-uniformity sampling technique of Chan *et al.* [SODA 2012] by bounding the *shallow*
 17 *cell complexity* of the (unbounded) radius- r ball system to be linear in n . To this end we have two
 18 technical innovations:

- 19 1. The discrete ball system on planar graphs are neither pseudodisks nor have well-defined boundaries
 20 for standard union-complexity arguments. We construct a *support graph* for arbitrary distance
 21 ball systems as contractions of Voronoi cells; the sparseness comes as a byproduct.
- 22 2. We present an assignment of each depth- (≥ 3) cell to a unique 3-tuple of ball centers. This allows
 23 us to use standard Clarkson-Shor techniques to reduce the counting to cells of depth *exactly* 3,
 24 which we prove to be size $O(n)$ by a novel geometric argument based on our support being a
 25 Voronoi contraction.

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26 **1** Introduction

27 The concept of *distance balls* is of fundamental importance to any given metric space (X, d)
 28 as the concept of *open sets* to any topological space. A *distance ball* $B(v, r)$ in a metric space
 29 (X, d) with radius r centered at point v is the subset of points $\{u \in X : d(u, v) \leq r\}$ in X .
 30 Many of the algorithmic success on graphs can be attributed to new understandings of the
 31 structure of distance balls in the corresponding graph metric.

32 **The role of distance balls.** Take the *minimum dominating set*—one of the 21 famous
 33 NP-complete problems of Karp—as an example. Given an unweighted graph G , the *minimum*
 34 *dominating set problem* (DOMINATING SET for short) asks for a subset of vertices S of smallest
 35 cardinality, such that every vertex in G is either in S , or is adjacent to some vertex in S .
 36 DOMINATING SET can also be interpreted as an instance of the *set cover problem*: Consider
 37 the set $\mathcal{R} := \{B(v, 1) : v \in V_G\}$ of 1-neighborhood balls. Observe that a set S is dominating
 38 in G if and only if every vertex is covered by the subset of 1-neighborhood balls in \mathcal{R} centered
 39 in S . In other words, a minimum solution of the set-cover instance (V_G, \mathcal{R}) is a minimum
 40 dominating set in G . This simple observation immediately implies an $O(\log n)$ -approximation
 41 to DOMINATING SET, where n is the number of nodes in G , by the standard greedy set cover
 42 algorithm. $O(\log n)$ -approximation is the best possible (under popular beliefs in complexity)
 43 if we make no further assumptions on the graph [26, 15]; this is essentially because the
 44 interaction between 1-neighborhood balls in general graphs can be complex and unruly.

45 What if we consider special classes of graphs with additional geometry constraints? One
 46 of the most well-studied examples is *planar graphs*, graphs with a drawing in the plane
 47 where no two edges cross each other. Planar graphs exhibit many helpful traits for algorithm
 48 design; particularly, several partitioning tools exist, including *separators* [44, 48, 60], *low-*
 49 *diameter decompositions* [42, 4, 9], and an algorithmic paradigm now famously known as
 50 *Baker’s shifting/layering technique* [1] which utilizes diameter-treewidth property [23] and
 51 the decomposability of planar graphs into k -outerplanar graphs. The idea is to compute a
 52 BFS-tree from an arbitrary node, then focus only on a few consecutive layers at a time. If the
 53 optimization problem at hand is *local* (for DOMINATING SET, node coverage can be checked
 54 by examining immediate neighbors), then a major portion of the optimal solution would be
 55 preserved within the consecutive layers. By iterating over the initial shift value and removing
 56 one out of every $O(1/\varepsilon)$ layers in the BFS-tree, one may guarantee a $(1 + \varepsilon)$ -approximation
 57 to the optimal solution. This is the main idea behind the polynomial-time approximation
 58 scheme (PTAS) of DOMINATING SET on unweighted planar graphs [1].

59 Not surprisingly, the same layering technique can be applied to the *r -dominating set*
 60 *problem* (r -DOMINATING SET for short) in planar graphs for any absolute constant r , where
 61 the goal is similar to DOMINATING SET but every node in S can “cover” a vertex subset of
 62 radius r [18]. r -DOMINATING SET was introduced by Barilan, Kortsarz, and Peleg [3] and
 63 later rediscovered in several other context [31, 18]. However, one encounters some trouble
 64 when generalizing Baker’s technique to minor-free graphs. This is because arbitrary minor-
 65 free graph no longer satisfies the diameter-treewidth property (imagine adding one extra
 66 vertex connecting to every node in a planar graph; the diameter becomes 2 but the graph is
 67 K_6 -minor-free). One possible way to overcome the issue is to apply the Robertson-Seymour
 68 structural theorem for minor-free graphs [34, 59], which seems to be overkill. Another,
 69 possibly more satisfying solution, is to understand what the $O(1)$ -radius neighborhood balls
 70 can look like in a minor-free graph. This is the route taken by the *local search* approach.
 71 On planar graphs, typical local search analysis [10] is usually done by applying an *exchange*
 72 *argument* on the base graph G , utilizing the fact that planar graphs have small separators [44]

73 (in the form of an r -division [30]). Har-Peled and Quanrud [36] observed that, for problems like
 74 r -dominating set, the exchange argument in a typical local search analysis can be performed
 75 on the *intersection graph* of $O(1)$ -neighborhood balls [49, 12] (more accurately, the subgraph
 76 $G_{\mathcal{R}}$ induced by the union of the local search solution and the optimal solution). They
 77 further observed that the intersection graph $G_{\mathcal{R}}$ over $O(1)$ -radius balls in minor-free graph
 78 G , while not necessarily itself minor-free, must have *polynomial expansion* [51]. Without
 79 going into definitions, the class of graphs with polynomial expansion coincide with those that
 80 have sublinear-size separators for all subgraphs [21]. Thus one can apply the same kind of
 81 exchange argument using separator decomposition on the ball intersection graph $G_{\mathcal{R}}$.

82 **Arbitrary radii and arbitrary weights.** The r -dominating set problem becomes significantly
 83 harder when r can depend on n [22]. In the literature this is usually refer to as the
 84 the *metric/unbounded r -dominating set problem* [27, 28], where we further allow arbitrary
 85 nonnegative *edge-length* ℓ on the input graph, in addition to the covering radius r (now
 86 measuring with respect to ℓ) becoming part of the input. We can even consider a weighted
 87 variant of the problem, where every vertex is associated with a positive-valued *weight* w , and
 88 the goal is to compute an r -dominating set with minimum total weight (instead of minimum
 89 cardinality). Baker’s layering technique no longer applies, nor does the local search strategy
 90 for the most part. (There is an exception [43, 27] which we will talk about in the technical
 91 section.) This is somewhat expected because the unbounded r -dominating set problem
 92 is no longer “local”, and the intersection graph of radius- r balls may be dense and have
 93 complex interactions. In fact, under Exponential-Time Hypothesis, Fox-Epstein *et al.* [45, 29]
 94 proved that no efficient PTAS can exist for the unbounded r -dominating set problem on
 95 planar graphs. Thus, recent work has resorted to *bicriteria* algorithms, allowing the returned
 96 solution to use a dominating set of radius $(1 + \varepsilon)r$ instead, in addition to the total weight
 97 being a $1 + \varepsilon$ approximation to the optimal value [22, 29]. The idea is to embed the original
 98 planar/minor-free graph metric into some other *tree-like metrics*, where the r -dominating set
 99 problem can easily be solved using dynamic programming. Unfortunately one has to suffer
 100 some form of distortion (which translates to the slack in covering radius); the best result
 101 so far gives $+\varepsilon\Delta$ -additive embedding of diameter- Δ minor-free graphs into graphs of $O_{\varepsilon}(1)$
 102 treewidth [13, 14]. This line of research has been fruitful and ultimately leads to bicriteria
 103 EPTAS for planar graphs [29] and bicriteria Q(Q)PTAS for minor-free graphs [27, 28].

104 But what if we really want to solve the unbounded r -dominating set problem without
 105 compromise on the radius r ? The lower bound result [45, 29] leaves us no choice but to look
 106 at $O(1)$ -approximation (or at least, $(1 + \varepsilon)$ -approximation with running time $n^{f(\varepsilon)}$). The
 107 existence of such algorithm was explicitly asked by Filtser and Le [28].

108 **Our contribution.** We establish the first polynomial-time $O(1)$ -approximation algorithm for
 109 the (vertex)-weighted metric r -dominating set problem for unbounded r . We emphasize that
 110 r is part of the input, and can be arbitrarily large compared to n .

111 ► **Theorem 1.** *Let G be an arbitrary n -node planar graph, where each vertex v is associated*
 112 *with a weight $w(v)$. Let r be an arbitrary radius parameter. There is a polynomial-time*
 113 *algorithm that computes an r -dominating set in G whose weight is $O(1)$ times the optimum.*

114 1.1 Techniques

115 Our new (single-criteria) $O(1)$ -approximation algorithm for weighted r -dominating set on
 116 planar graphs uses the quasi-uniformity sampling technique, originally designed for weighted

117 set cover problem on geometric shapes [64, 11]. But first, we have to describe a bit of
 118 (technical) history and two immediate challenges when adapting to our setting.

119 **Challenge 1: Planar support.** Geometric set cover problems have their own history and
 120 success [7, 16, 17, 63]. Notably, for an unweighted set cover instance (X, \mathcal{R}) , the result
 121 of Brönnimann and Goodrich [7] provided a recipe to achieve $O(1)$ -approximation. Their
 122 pioneering use of multiplicative weight update algorithm requires the existence of small
 123 ε -net: First, find an ε -net N for the dual set system (\mathcal{R}, X) (notice that here the ε -net is
 124 in the dual and thus a subset of ranges in \mathcal{R}). If there are element x in X not covered by
 125 N , double the weight of every range in \mathcal{R} that covers x , to increase the chance of choosing
 126 one such range in the next round. As a result, by setting $\varepsilon = \Theta(1/\text{opt})$, this implies an
 127 $O(g(\text{opt}))$ -approximation for any set cover instance, given the dual system has an ε -net of
 128 size $O(\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \cdot g(\frac{1}{\varepsilon}))$. (See [25] for an LP interpretation and a simpler proof.)

129 For set system of bounded VC-dimension [62], there is always an ε -net of size $O(\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \log \frac{1}{\varepsilon})$ [37].
 130 Also, if the VC-dimension of a primal system is d , then the dual system has VC-dimension at
 131 most 2^d [35]. To get $O(1)$ -approximation, however, we need a much stronger assumption of
 132 $O(\frac{1}{\varepsilon})$ -size ε -net in the dual system. This is not always achievable even for simple geometric
 133 shapes like lines and rectangles [50]; in fact, among the basic geometric shapes, only a handful
 134 are known to have linear-size ε -net, including halfspaces in 2D and 3D [47, 52, 46], unit-cubes
 135 in 3D [17], and family of pseudodisks in the plane (both primal and dual) [54].

136 For our application of unbounded r -dominating set problem, the “geometric shapes” are
 137 the radius- r balls in planar graphs, which is discrete in nature, lacking well-defined boundary
 138 curves to even make the definition of pseudodisks meaningful. One might sneer at the issue
 139 and say, “there must be a way; how can distance balls in the plane be much different from
 140 pseudodisks?” But even if we redefine the notion of pseudodisks combinatorially (for every
 141 pair of regions A and B , all three sets $A \cap B$, $A \setminus B$, and $B \setminus A$ are connected), the distance
 142 balls are still not pseudodisk. In fact, they can be *piercing* in the sense of Raman-Ray [55],
 143 as illustrated by Figure 1.

■ **Figure 1.** Two distance balls R and R' that are piercing. Here both R and R' have radius 6.

144 Fortunately, Pyrga and Ray [54] provided an alternative method to obtain linear-size
 145 ε -net (in the dual) — to construct a *sparse support* for the primal system (X, \mathcal{R}) . We say
 146 a set system (X, \mathcal{R}) has a *support*, if for any subsystem $(X', \mathcal{R}_{|X'})$ of (X, \mathcal{R}) , there is an
 147 undirected graph H on the elements of X' such that for every set R in $\mathcal{R}_{|X'}$, the subgraph
 148 H_R of H induced by the elements of R is connected. The support is *sparse* if every such
 149 graph H is sparse. The work of Pyrga and Ray [54] implies that if (X, \mathcal{R}) has bounded
 150 VC-dimension and a sparse support, then the dual system (X, \mathcal{R}) has ε -net of size $O(\frac{1}{\varepsilon})$.

151 Our first technical contribution is to compute a support for any collection of distance balls
 152 in any *arbitrary* graph (not just planar graphs). Crucially, if the given graph is planar, then
 153 so is the support. We remind the reader that our original goal is to solve the r -dominating
 154 set problem with unbounded r ; thus the construction of the support has to hold for balls of
 155 unbounded radii as well. This is the first construction of its kind; most previous work on

156 sparse support focus on geometric shapes, and almost entirely restricted to *planar support*
 157 for set systems that are pseudodisks [54] and their generalizations [55]. For piercing systems
 158 like axis-parallel rectangles, there are configurations where no planar support can exist [53].

159 Instead of focusing on planarity, we shift the narrative by arguing that a support graph
 160 for (X, \mathcal{R}) is really a *connectivity sketch* that exists for every graph G on X , as long as the
 161 sets in \mathcal{R} are *distance balls* on G . Our construction for support on arbitrary balls in G can be
 162 described simply as follows: Build a *Voronoi diagram* of $V(G)$ with respect to balls centers,
 163 then contract every Voronoi cell into a single node. We argue that the contracted graph is
 164 a support of G . (The benefit of this additional property becomes evident when we tackle
 165 the next challenge.) Both planarity and sparseness come as a byproduct of the fact that
 166 contraction of the Voronoi diagram is a *minor* of G . (See Theorem 2 for a precise statement.)
 167 (A similar Voronoi diagram idea can be found in the work of Le [43, 27]; but their version
 168 only enables single-criteria algorithm for *unweighted* metric r -dominating set problem.)

169 **Challenge 2: Linear shallow cell complexity.** There is another, perhaps more severe,
 170 obstacle to overcome. We want to solve the *weighted* version of the r -dominating set problem.
 171 The Brönnimann-Goodrich MWU approach relies on computing regular ε -net (as subset of
 172 balls covering the vertices); the *size* bound on ε -net translates to approximation guarantee
 173 on *size* of the cover, and thus can only work in the unweighted setting. Varadarajan [64]
 174 extended the ε -net idea to the weighted setting. This *quasi-uniformity sampling technique*
 175 computes ε -nets that samples each set in \mathcal{R} with (roughly) equal probability, which then
 176 can be made aware of the weights on \mathcal{R} . Chan, Grant, Könemann, and Sharpe [11] later
 177 polished this technique and made connection to a more refined measure on set systems called
 178 *shallow cell complexity*. In our context, cell complexity refers to the number of different
 179 equivalent classes (called *cells*) of points that are covered by the same subset of r -balls. We
 180 say a cell has *depth* k if the points within are covered by up to k balls. A set system has
 181 shallow cell complexity $f(|\mathcal{R}|, k)$ if the number of cells of depth at most k is bounded by
 182 $f(|\mathcal{R}|, k)$; for the purpose of obtaining $O(1)$ -approximation for set cover, one requires the
 183 shallow cell complexity to be $O(|\mathcal{R}| \cdot \text{poly } k)$.

184 The quasi-uniformity sampling technique can be used to solve the *constant* r case for
 185 weighted r -dominating set problem on minor-free graphs (and graphs with bounded expansion
 186 as well [20]). This is because in the case of constant radius r , the *whole* cell complexity is
 187 linearly bounded [58, 39], which directly bounds the shallow counterpart. Unfortunately, it
 188 is known that the cell complexity of r -balls on a planar graph can be cubic in r [39], and
 189 thus cannot help in the unbounded r setting.

190 One way to see why halfspaces and pseudodisks are special is that they both have linear
 191 *union complexity* [41, 17]. Application of the classical Clarkson-Shor technique then implies
 192 that the shallow cell complexity is bounded by $O(|\mathcal{R}| \cdot k)$. When working with arbitrary-radius
 193 balls on graphs however, we run into trouble applying Clarkson-Shor. First, there is no
 194 well-defined notion of union complexity for a collection of subgraphs. One would imagine
 195 the support can take the role as the linear-size object at the base case for Clarkson-Shor;
 196 but this intuition is insufficient. The main issue is that for pseudodisks, the number of cells
 197 can be charged to the complexity of the whole pseudodisk arrangement by Euler's formula,
 198 and every crossing in the arrangement is uniquely defined by two pseudodisks. There is no
 199 immediate equivalent object for distance balls that allows for such counting.

200 Our solution is to reimagine the unique representative argument by Raman and Ray for
 201 the non-piercing family [56]; the new proof is substantially different and relies on geometric
 202 properties of distance balls, instead of topological properties of curve sweeping [56, §6]. First
 203 we argue that every cell can be charged to a unique 3-tuple of ball centers (Lemma 7). This

223 ■ **Figure 2.** A set system with a dual support. The red regions containing the violet vertex v form a connected
 224 subgraph in the support.

204 allows us to apply Clarkson-Shor and reduce the problem to counting cells of depth 1, 2, and
 205 3. Depth 1 and 2 are straightforward; for depth-3 cells, we exploit the additional property
 206 that our support for distance balls came from contracting *Voronoi cells* with respect to the
 207 ball centers, and thus the number of depth-3 cells can be counted towards the complexity of
 208 the Voronoi diagram, which is asymptotically the same as the planar support (Lemma 13).

209 2 Terminology and Support Graphs

210 Let's first introduce the terminology needed for concrete discussion. Our support construction
 211 actually works for balls in an arbitrary *directed* graph. We refer to the digraph that our ball
 212 system lives on as the *underlying graph* G . Note that all results apply to balls in undirected
 213 graphs. A *ball* D can be defined using a pair (c_D, r_D) where c_D is a vertex of G called the
 214 *center*, and a *radius* r_D which is a real number. Ball D is then defined to be the set of all
 215 vertices v whose shortest path from c_D has length at most r_D .

216 Given a system (U, \mathcal{R}) , the *dual system* (\mathcal{R}, U) has the elements of U treated as subsets of
 217 \mathcal{R} : if element e in U is a member of set R in \mathcal{R} in the primal system, then R is a member of
 218 *set* e in the dual system. We use the term *dual support* of (U, \mathcal{R}) to refer to a support graph
 219 of the dual system (\mathcal{R}, U) . (We give an example of a dual support in Figure 2.) Although
 220 our r -dominating set application demands primal support, the set system of balls of *equal*
 221 *radius* is self-dual. Thus, we do not differentiate the support for the primal from the dual,
 222 but instead describe the support for the dual system since it is conceptually easier.

225 In Section 3 we construct a dual support for any system of balls, by contracting cells of
 226 the Voronoi diagram of the underlying graph (with respect to ball centers) into a minor.

227 ► **Theorem 2 (Support).** *Any system of balls \mathcal{R} on an underlying digraph G has a dual*
 228 *support $H(\mathcal{R})$ such that if G does not contain a minor K with minimum vertex degree two,*
 229 *then neither does $H(\mathcal{R})$.*

230 *Remark.* Unfortunately the min-degree requirement cannot be dropped in general. For
 231 example, if G is P_2 -minor-free, we have a set of disjoint vertices. But two balls can be centered
 232 on the same vertex, and thus connected in the dual support, which implies the existence
 233 of an edge and so the support is not P_2 -minor-free. Still the restriction is not severe as
 234 most of the interesting minor-free graph classes satisfy the min-degree condition, including
 235 K_h -minors for $h \geq 3$, grid minors, and all forbidden minors for bounded-genus graphs.

236 Since planar graphs can be classified by their excluded minors, these results imply a
 237 planar dual support for the ball system \mathcal{R} on G . We then proceed to show that \mathcal{R} has linear
 238 shallow cell complexity in Section 4.

239 ► **Theorem 3** (Shallow Cell Complexity). *Let G be a planar graph. Any system of balls (V_G, \mathcal{R})*
 240 *has shallow cell complexity $O(|\mathcal{R}| \cdot k^2)$.*

241 2.1 Applications

242 In addition to the result on computing unbounded r -dominating set in planar graphs, the
 243 supports also have their own implications. An important property of our support construction
 244 is that we only ever contract edges that are within radius r of a ball center. This means that if
 245 G is an unweighted graph with *polynomial expansion* and we are considering constant-radius
 246 balls, the support graph will also have polynomial expansion, allowing us to use the sublinear
 247 separators from Har-Peled and Quanrud [36] to get the same PTAS results for unweighted
 248 problems as Raman and Ray [55] achieved for non-piercing regions. If r is not bounded by a
 249 constant, we can achieve the same when G is minor-free [66].

250 Another natural use of supports is for problems relating to geodesic disks in a polygonal
 251 domain (possibly with holes). It is known that planar metrics and polygonal domains are
 252 *equivalent*: any system of geodesic disks in a polygonal domain in \mathbb{R}^2 can be represented as
 253 a system of balls in a planar graph, and vice versa [6]. By the equivalence, our techniques
 254 naturally give planar supports for geodesic disks in polygonal domains.

255 2.2 Related Work on Support Graphs

256 Van Cleemput [61] and Voloshina and Feinberg [65] used the existence of a planar support
 257 graph to give meaningful notion of planarity in the hypergraph setting. As such, support
 258 graphs have seen interest in (hyper)graph drawing community [38, 40, 8]. In the realm of
 259 optimization, Pyrga and Ray [54] used support graphs to construct linear-sized ε -nets for
 260 several set systems with bounded VC dimension, including halfspaces in \mathbb{R}^3 and pseudodisks
 261 (more generally, r -admissible regions) in \mathbb{R}^2 . Here the support graphs were required to be
 262 *sparse* (i.e. with linearly many edges) in order to bootstrap existing ε -net sizes down to $O(\frac{1}{\varepsilon})$.
 263 Later on support graphs that are *planar* were used by Mustafa and Ray [49] to show a PTAS
 264 for various optimization problem in the geometric setting. Instead of ε -net, they exploited
 265 the existence of *sublinear-size* separators in planar graphs to show that an $O_\varepsilon(1)$ -swap local
 266 search algorithm gives a $(1 + \varepsilon)$ -approximation for minimum geometric hitting set. The
 267 same paradigm of analyzing local search with separators on planar support was extended
 268 to other problems, such as maximum independent set and generalized set cover (including
 269 dominating set and hitting set) in pseudodisks and non-piercing regions [12, 19, 33, 55],
 270 terrain guarding [32, 2], and covering the boundary of a simple orthogonal polygon with
 271 rectangles [5]. (A survey on the many use of support can be found in Raman and Singh [57].)

272 3 Existence of Support Graph

273 To begin constructing the dual support for a system of balls \mathcal{R} in a graph G , we will first
 274 modify G slightly and reduce to the case where *every ball in \mathcal{R} has the same radius*. We
 275 will refer to the new graph as G' . (Recall we work with the general case of digraphs.) We
 276 augment digraph G by adding a new node corresponding to each ball in \mathcal{R} . (For clarity, we
 277 refer to original vertices of G as *vertices* and new vertices corresponding to \mathcal{R} as *nodes*.) For
 278 each ball R in \mathcal{R} , we create a single node, x_R , which has only one edge: an outgoing edge
 279 into c_R , the center of the ball R . We give the edge a weight of $r_{\max} - r_R$, where r_{\max} is
 280 defined to be $\max_{R' \in \mathcal{R}} r_{R'}$. This allows us to instead consider each R in \mathcal{R} to be centered at
 281 x_R , all with the same radius r_{\max} , and the balls will still define the same set system \mathcal{R} over

282 the vertices in G . Finally, remove all vertices which are not contained in any ball of \mathcal{R} and
 283 slightly perturb the edge weights (without changing any ball containment relations) so that
 284 every vertex v has a unique closest ball center in $\{x_R : R \in \mathcal{R}\}$.

285 To build the dual support, we construct a *Voronoi partition* of G' with respect to the set
 286 of nodes. A *Voronoi partition* \mathcal{F} of a graph G' with respect to a set of nodes S is a partition
 287 of $V_{G'}$ into subsets such that for every node $R \in S$, there is a corresponding subset $F_R \in \mathcal{F}$
 288 which contains all vertices u in G' for which $d(x_R, u) \leq \min_{x_{R'} \in S \setminus \{x_R\}} d(x_{R'}, u)$. For clarity,
 289 we will refer to each set F_R in \mathcal{F} as the *Voronoi cell* of R . In our case, we construct the
 290 Voronoi partition $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{R}}$ of G' with respect to $\{x_R : R \in \mathcal{R}\}$, which we identify as \mathcal{R} . Each
 291 cell F_R in the Voronoi partition is a connected subset of G' because for every vertex v in F_R
 292 reachable from x_R , the vertices on the shortest path between x_R and v must belong to F_R
 293 as well. Thus we can simply contract every F in $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{R}}$ to a (contraction)-minor on only the
 294 nodes in \mathcal{R} . This final graph H , we claim, is a dual support for (G, \mathcal{R}) .

295 ■ **Figure 3.** An illustration of the proof to Lemma 4 that π can only pass through Voronoi cells of \mathcal{R}_v . The
 296 purple region is the Voronoi cell F_Q

297 ► **Lemma 4.** For any vertex v in G' , the set of balls $\mathcal{R}_v \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ that contain v must induce a
 298 connected subgraph in H .

299 **Proof.** Consider any vertex v which is contained in at least two balls in \mathcal{R} . Vertex v must
 300 be in the Voronoi cell F_R of some ball R by construction of G' . We claim that for any other
 301 ball R' of \mathcal{R} that also contains v , there is a path from $x_{R'}$ to v in G' , denoted as π , that
 302 only passes through Voronoi cells corresponding to balls that contain v .

303 Since we have removed all vertices which have no incoming path from any ball, every
 304 vertex along π in G' must be in some cell. Assume that some vertex u along π is contained
 305 in some Voronoi cell F_Q corresponding to a ball Q that does not contain v . By definition of
 306 Voronoi cell, we have that $d(x_Q, u) \leq d(x_{R'}, u)$. By the definition of shortest paths, we know
 307 that $d(x_{R'}, v) = d(x_{R'}, u) + d(u, v)$. By triangle inequality, we then have the following:

$$308 \quad d(x_Q, v) \leq d(x_Q, u) + d(u, v) \leq d(x_{R'}, u) + d(u, v) = d(x_{R'}, v).$$

309 But, $d(x_{R'}, v) \leq r_{\max}$ and $d(x_Q, v) > r_{\max}$ since v is in R' but not in Q , contradiction. ◀

310 **Proof of Theorem 2.** Construct H as described above. By Lemma 4, we know that H
 311 satisfies the definition of a dual support for system (V_G, \mathcal{R}) . It remains to show that if G
 312 has no minor K with minimum degree two, then neither can H . This is done by arguing
 313 that G' has no such minors, and then the fact that H is a minor of G' concludes the proof.

314 When constructing G' , we only perform two types of operations that would affect the
 315 existence of minors: deleting vertices and adding in nodes $\{x_R\}$ of degree one. Let K be
 316 a minor model (as a collection of disjoint vertex subsets called *supernodes*) of G' that has
 317 minimum degree two. If K only contains vertices but not nodes in G' , then K must appear
 318 in G as well (even though G' was obtained by removing some vertices from G). So at least
 319 one supernode η of K must contain some degree-1 x_R that was added in G' .

320 For an edge (η, η') to exist in K , there must be a vertex/node $u \in \eta$ and a vertex/node
 321 $u' \in \eta'$ such that (u, u') is an edge of G' . For η containing x_R , x_R must not be the only

322 vertex/node in η , since η have degree at least 2. Because η is connected, the neighbor of x_R
 323 is also in η and the (sole) edge incident on x_R must be contracted. This, however, means
 324 that there can be no edge (x_R, u') in G' that corresponds to an edge (η, η') in K , so there is
 325 a minor K' isomorphic to K where x_R was simply deleted and thus x_R is not in η . Since
 326 this holds for all x_R , there must be some minor of G isomorphic to K , a contradiction. ◀

327 4 Shallow Cell Complexity of Balls in Planar Graphs

328 Shallow cell complexity was introduced by Chan *et al.* [11] as a combinatorial analog of union
 329 complexity. We introduce the terminology within our context of distance balls on graphs.

330 Define the *hit set* of a vertex v with respect to \mathcal{R} to be the subset of balls in \mathcal{R} which
 331 contain v . A *cell* of the system (V_G, \mathcal{R}) is a set of vertices in V_G that have the same hit set
 332 of incident balls. *Cell complexity* is simply the number of cells in (V_G, \mathcal{R}) , where as *shallow*
 333 cell complexity counts the number of cells of a particular *depth* k in \mathcal{R} , denoted $Cell_k$, the
 334 equivalence classes of vertices whose hit set has size k . We say the set system has *shallow*
 335 *cell complexity* $f(n, k)$ if for depth k , there are at most $f(n, k)$ cells. Our goal for the section
 336 is to show that for a planar graph G , the shallow cell complexity for any system of balls
 337 (V_G, \mathcal{R}) is $O(|\mathcal{R}| \cdot k^2)$ (Theorem 3). Just as in the support constructions in §3, we again
 338 reduce to the case where *every ball in our system \mathcal{R} has the same radius.*

339 **Proof of Theorem 3.** We use two key lemmas proven later in the subsections. The first
 340 claims that for every cell c of depth k , there is a unique encoding of c , $\langle \alpha(c), \beta(c), \gamma(c) \rangle$,
 341 where each member of the tuple is a ball of \mathcal{R} (Lemma 7 in Section 4.1). Importantly, the
 342 encoding is unique among cells of depth k , not universally. This naively implies that there is
 343 at most $O(|\mathcal{R}|^3)$ cells of depth k . Using the standard Clarkson–Shor arguments argument,
 344 we can improve this to $O(|\mathcal{R}| \cdot k^2)$ if the number of cells of depth (at most) 3 is $O(|\mathcal{R}|)$
 345 (Lemma 13 in Section 4.2). More precisely: Sample the regions of \mathcal{R} with probability $1/k$. A
 346 cell c with unique encoding appears in the sample as depth-3 cell with probability at least
 347 $(ek)^{-3}$. The expected number of depth-3 cells in the sample is at most $O(|\mathcal{R}|/k)$, so the
 348 number of depth- k cells in \mathcal{R} is at most $O(|\mathcal{R}| \cdot k^2)$. ◀

349 4.1 Unique 3-Site Encoding of Cells

350 We begin by assigning each cell of $Cell_k$ an *unique* encoding for each fixed depth $k \geq 3$.
 351 This encoding will depend on the set of incident balls corresponding to c . Specifically, the
 352 encoding will be formed by a 3-tuple of regions in \mathcal{R} , which we will refer to as $\langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma \rangle$. In
 353 assigning the encoding, we do not modify to the set system at all. Instead, we fix an arbitrary
 354 vertex v_c for cell c as its *representative*. We denote the cell containing v as $Cell(v)$.

355 For a cell c , we begin by designating its $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ -*type*. We define $\alpha(v)$ as the furthest ball
 356 from v that contains v . Similarly, we define $\beta(v)$ as the second furthest ball from v that
 357 contains v . For cell c , its $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ -*type* is simply $\langle \alpha(v_c), \beta(v_c) \rangle$. (Notice that $\alpha(v_c)$ and $\beta(v_c)$
 358 might be different if one chooses a different v_c from cell c , and thus the $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ -type of c
 359 depends on its representative.) Let $\pi_{\alpha, \beta}(v)$ be the union of $\pi(\alpha(v), v)$ and $\pi(\beta(v), v)$, where
 360 $\pi(x, y)$ is the shortest path from x to y in G .

363 ▶ **Lemma 5.** *For a vertex v with $\alpha(v) = D_1$ and $\beta(v) = D_2$, every vertex v' in $\pi_{\alpha, \beta}(v)$ with*
 364 *$\alpha(v') = D_1$ and $\beta(v') = D_2$ satisfies $hit(v') \subseteq hit(v)$.*

365 **Proof.** Assume the contrary. Then, there is some vertex v' which is contained within some
 366 ball D_3 such that $v \notin D_3$. By definition of α and β , it must be that the center of D_3 is closer

361 **Figure 4.** Given two vertices v, v' satisfying $\alpha(v) = \alpha(v') = D_1$, $\beta(v) = \beta(v') = D_2$ and $v' \in \pi(D_1, v)$,
 362 any ball D_3 containing v' must also contain v .

367 to v' than D_1 and D_2 . However, since v' is either in $\pi(c_{D_1}, v)$ or $\pi(c_{D_2}, v)$, this means that
 368 D_3 is closer to v than one of D_1 or D_2 , and thus D_3 must contain v , a contradiction by the
 369 assumption that all balls have equal radius. (See Figure 4.) ◀

370 The third component of our encoding, γ , can now be defined. For $k = 3$, γ is simply
 371 the remaining ball after removing α and β . For $k \geq 4$, we define γ procedurally after fixing
 372 α, β . Denote the set of all cells of depth k with $\alpha(v_c) = D_1$ and $\beta(v_c) = D_2$ as $C_k(D_1, D_2)$.
 373 We additionally collect the representatives v_c of each $c \in C_k(D_1, D_2)$ into a corresponding
 374 set $V_k(D_1, D_2)$. Let $T_D(S)$ be the shortest path tree from the center x_D of a ball D to
 375 a set of vertices S . Consider the shortest path tree $T_{D_1}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$. We will process all
 376 $v_c \in V_k(D_1, D_2)$ using the plane drawing of $T_{D_1}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$.

377 Perform a depth-first traversal starting at x_D , processing children in clockwise order. The
 378 depth-first traversal $T_{D_1}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$ of gives a total ordering of the vertices in $V_k(D_1, D_2)$,
 379 which also induces a total ordering σ on the corresponding cells $C_k(D_1, D_2)$. For brevity, we
 380 will index the cells based on their order in σ (the i th cell as c_i) in a cyclic manner. For the i th
 381 cell c_i in the total ordering, we assign $\gamma(c_i)$ to be an arbitrary ball D with $D \in \text{hit}(v_{c_i})$ and
 382 $D \notin \text{hit}(v_{c_{i-1}})$. Since $|\text{hit}(v_{c_i})| = |\text{hit}(v_{c_{i-1}})| = k$ and $\text{hit}(v_{c_i}) \neq \text{hit}(v_{c_{i-1}})$ (by the definition
 383 of cell), such a D must always exist, and thus we can assign $\gamma(c_i)$ to all cells.

384 We now show that this definition of γ is sufficient to ensure that each distinct cell c of
 385 size k has a unique encoding. First, we use Lemma 5 to show that the representative vertices
 386 of cells with the same α and β cannot form ancestor relationships in $T_{D_1}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$.

387 **Observation 6.** For any two distinct cells $c, c' \in C_k(D_1, D_2)$, v_c cannot be an ancestor of
 388 $v_{c'}$ in $T_{D_1}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$ or $T_{D_2}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$.

389 **Proof.** First consider $T_{D_1}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$. If v_c were an ancestor of $v_{c'}$, then v_c would be in
 390 $\pi(D_1, v_{c'})$. This would imply that $\text{hit}(v_{c'}) \subseteq \text{hit}(v_c)$ by Lemma 5. However, since c and c'
 391 have depth k , $|\text{hit}(v_c)| = |\text{hit}(v_{c'})| = k$. The subset relationship would hence require that
 392 $\text{hit}(v_c) = \text{hit}(v_{c'})$, and thus c and c' are the same class, which is a contradiction. A symmetric
 393 argument applies for $T_{D_2}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$. ◀

394 This means that for any c, c' with the same α and β , $\pi(\alpha(v_c), v_c) \not\subseteq \pi(\alpha(v_{c'}), v_{c'})$.

395 **Lemma 7.** For $k \geq 3$, every cell c of depth k has a unique encoding $\langle \alpha(c), \beta(c), \gamma(c) \rangle \in \mathcal{R}^3$.

396 **Proof.** If two cells have the same depth and α and β , they are both indexed by the same traversal
 397 order σ . Consider two cells c_i, c_j such that $\langle \alpha(c_i), \beta(c_i), \gamma(c_i) \rangle = \langle \alpha(c_j), \beta(c_j), \gamma(c_j) \rangle =$
 398 (D_1, D_2, D_3) and $|\text{hit}(v_{c_i})| = |\text{hit}(v_{c_j})| = k$.

399 We need to consider how c_i and c_j were assigned the same γ . Recall that we force adjacent
 400 cells c_{i-1}, c_i to not just have different γ assignments, but that the $\gamma(c_i)$ not contain $\gamma(c_{i-1})$.
 401 This forces $v_{c_{i-1}}$ and $v_{c_{j-1}}$ to not be contained by D_3 . Let a be the lowest common ancestor
 402 of $v_{c_{i-1}}$ and $v_{c_{j-1}}$ in $T_{D_1}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$. Similarly, let b be the lowest common ancestor of $v_{c_{i-1}}$
 403 and $v_{c_{j-1}}$ in $T_{D_2}(V_k(D_1, D_2))$. We consider the cycle F formed by the union of the following

404 shortest paths: $\pi(a, v_{c_{i-1}})$ to $\pi(v_{c_{i-1}}, b)$ to $\pi(b, v_{c_{j-1}})$ to $\pi(v_{c_{j-1}}, a)$. Since G is planar, F
 405 describes the boundary of some region $R(F)$. Since $i-1 < i < j-1 < j$, by the definition of
 406 our traversal one of v_{c_i} or v_{c_j} lies in $R(F)$ and the other lies outside. (We give an example
 407 $R(F)$ as a gray region in Figure 5.) This means that, for D_3 to contain both v_{c_i} and v_{c_j} , D_3
 408 must also contain some vertex u' of F . Assume WLOG that u' lies on $\pi(D_3, v_{c_j})$. Since u'
 409 lies on F , it must be on one of $\pi(D_1, v_{c_{i-1}})$, $\pi(D_1, v_{c_{j-1}})$, $\pi(D_2, v_{c_{i-1}})$, or $\pi(D_2, v_{c_{j-1}})$.

- 410 ■ If u' is in $\pi(D_1, v_{c_{i-1}})$ or $\pi(D_1, v_{c_{j-1}})$, then we know that D_3 must be further from u'
 411 than D_1 since D_3 cannot contain $v_{c_{i-1}}$ or $v_{c_{j-1}}$. However, since $\alpha(v_{c_j}) = D_1$, D_3 must
 412 be closer to u' than D_1 since u' is on $\pi(D_3, v_{c_j})$ and $\alpha(v_{c_j})$ is the furthest ball from v_{c_j}
 413 which still contains it. (See left subfigure of Figure 5.)
- 414 ■ Similarly, if u' is in $\pi(D_2, v_{c_{i-1}})$ or $\pi(D_2, v_{c_{j-1}})$, then D_3 must be further from u' than
 415 D_2 since D_3 cannot contain $v_{c_{i-1}}$ or $v_{c_{j-1}}$. However, since $\beta(v_{c_j}) = D_2$, D_3 must be
 416 closer to u' than D_2 since u' is on $\pi(D_3, v_{c_j})$ and $\beta(v_{c_j})$ is the second furthest ball from
 417 v_{c_j} , while D_3 is at best third furthest. (See right subfigure of Figure 5.)

418 ■ **Figure 5.** If two cells c_i, c_j have the same $\gamma(c_i) = \gamma(c_j) = D_3$, then there must D_3 must contain a vertex
 419 u' of $\gamma_{\alpha, \beta}(v_{c_{j-1}})$ or $\gamma_{\alpha, \beta}(v_{c_{i-1}})$. The region $R(F)$ corresponding to the simple cycle F is given in gray.
 420 Left: u' is in $\pi(D_1, v_{c_{j-1}})$. Right: u' is in $\pi(D_2, v_{c_{j-1}})$.

421 We get a contradiction in both cases, which means that $\gamma(c_i)$ cannot equal $\gamma(c_j)$, and
 422 thus every cell c of the same depth $k \geq 3$ must have a unique encoding $\langle \alpha(c), \beta(c), \gamma(c) \rangle$. ◀

4.2 Depth-3 Cells

423
 424 Now that we have a unique encoding $\langle \alpha(v_c), \beta(v_c), \gamma(v_c) \rangle$ for every cell c of depth k , we can
 425 proceed to give a bound on $|Cell_3|$.

426 For each c in $Cell_3$, we consider its encoding $\langle \alpha(v_c), \beta(v_c), \gamma(v_c) \rangle$. Since c only has depth
 427 3, we know that these are simply the balls of $hit(v_c)$, placed in order of distance from v_c . Our
 428 first step is to select one of the three balls of $hit(v_c)$ as $base(v_c)$. Next, we iterate through
 429 every ball D in \mathcal{R} and count the number of cells that have been assigned D . We accomplish
 430 this by constructing a planar graph G_D on the neighbors of D in the Voronoi partition graph
 431 H . Summing over all D , this yields a total count of $O(|\mathcal{R}|)$ cells. We start with an important
 432 lemma regarding the order of distances to balls from vertices that lie on a shortest path.

433 ► **Lemma 8.** *Given any ball D of \mathcal{R} , a vertex v , some vertex v' on $\pi(x_D, v)$, and a distinct*
 434 *ball $D' \in \mathcal{R}$, if $d(x_{D'}, v') \leq d(x_D, v')$, then for all $v'' \in \pi(v', v)$, $d(x_{D'}, v'') \leq d(x_D, v'')$.*

435 **Proof.** For any $v'' \in \pi(v', v)$, because v' is between x_D and v'' on $\pi(x_D, v)$, $d(x_D, v'') =$
 436 $d(x_D, v') + d(v', v'')$. We also know that $d(x_{D'}, v'') \leq d(x_{D'}, v') + d(v', v'')$. Since $d(x_{D'}, v') \leq$
 437 $d(x_D, v')$, we can simply plug in to get $d(x_{D'}, v'') \leq d(x_D, v') + d(v', v'') = d(x_D, v'')$. ◀

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438 ► **Observation 9.** For a cell c and ball $D' \in \text{hit}(v_c)$, all vertices v in $\pi(x_D, v_c)$ must lie in
 439 the Voronoi cell of a ball in $\text{hit}(v_c)$.

440 **Proof.** Consider a ball $D' \notin \text{hit}(v_c)$ for which a vertex v of $\pi(x_D, v_c)$ lies in the Voronoi cell
 441 $F_{D'}$. If this is the case, then all the vertices after v in $\pi(x_D, v_c)$ will be closer to D' than they
 442 are to D , and since D contains v_c , D' must also then contain v_c , which is a contradiction. ◀

443 This means that the shortest paths from the centers of the balls hit by v_c to the vertex v_c
 444 must stay within the Voronoi cells of $\text{hit}(v_c)$. This observation, paired with Lemma 8, allows
 445 us to define $\text{base}(v_c)$ based on $\pi(x_{\alpha(v_c)}, v_c)$. We consider two cases:

- 446 ■ *Case 1:* Some vertex v in $\pi(x_{\alpha(v_c)}, v_c)$ lies in $F_{\beta(v_c)}$. Assign $\text{base}(v_c) \leftarrow \beta(v_c)$.
- 447 ■ *Case 2:* No vertex v in $\pi(x_{\alpha(v_c)}, v_c)$ lies in $F_{\beta(v_c)}$. Assign $\text{base}(v_c) \leftarrow \gamma(v_c)$.

■ **Figure 6.** Showing the subwalk of Lemma 10 and how to select base . Left: Case 1. Right: Case 2.

448 Now that we have assigned every cell to a ball, we consider a ball D and the set $\text{resident}(D)$,
 449 which is the set of cells c with $\text{base}(c) = D$. We will consider the cells of $\text{resident}(D)$ in
 450 relation to the neighbors of D within the Voronoi partition graph H .

451 ► **Lemma 10.** For a ball D and every cell c of $\text{resident}(D)$, there is a subwalk π_c of $\pi_{\alpha, \beta}(v_c)$
 452 with the (nonempty set of) interior vertices lying in D and the end vertices lying in distinct
 453 neighbors D', D'' of D in H .

454 **Proof.** If cell c is a *case-1* cell, we have that a vertex v in $\pi(x_{\alpha(v_c)}, v_c)$ which lies in $F_{\beta(v_c)}$.
 455 By Lemma 8, no vertex of $\pi(v, v_c)$ can lie in $F_{\alpha(v_c)}$. Additionally, v_c must lie in $F_{\gamma(v_c)}$ by
 456 definition of α and β . Let u be the first vertex of $\pi(v, v_c)$ which lies in $F_{\gamma(v_c)}$. Let v' be last
 457 vertex of $\pi_{\alpha, \beta}(v_c)$ which lies in $F_{\alpha(v_c)}$. The subwalk $\pi_{\alpha, \beta}(v_c)[v', u]$ satisfies this condition.

458 If cell c is a *case-2* cell, we have no such vertex and $\pi(x_{\alpha(v_c)}, v_c)$ lies entirely in $\alpha(v_c)$
 459 or $\gamma(v_c)$. Let u be the last vertex of $\pi(x_{\alpha(v_c)}, v_c)$ which lies in $F_{\alpha(v_c)}$ and let u' be the last
 460 vertex of $\pi(x_{\beta(v_c)}, v_c)$ that lies in $F_{\beta(v_c)}$. We then can take our subpath to be $\pi_{\alpha, \beta}(v_c)[u, u']$,
 461 and this will satisfy the condition. ◀

462 We now consider the neighbors of D in the Voronoi support H , $N_H(D)$. In Lemma 10,
 463 the subwalk π_c of cell c in $\text{resident}(D)$ runs between the two balls of $\text{hit}(v_c) \setminus D$, both of
 464 which must be in $N_H(D)$ since H is simply the contraction of the Voronoi partition of G . We
 465 can now define a graph G_D on $N_H(D)$ to count the number of cells in $\text{resident}(D)$. For every
 466 cell c of $\text{resident}(D)$, add an edge e_c between the balls of $\text{hit}(v_c) \setminus D$. Since the underlying
 467 graph G is planar, we can sketch a drawing of G_D as follows:

468 To draw the curve ζ_c corresponding to cell c of $\text{resident}(D)$, we first consider the subpath
 469 π_c that we get from Lemma 10, using a plane drawing of G_D . Let v be the first endpoint of
 470 π_c lying in a ball D_1 and v' be the second endpoint of π_c lying in a ball D_2 . We first draw
 471 the center x_{D_1} in its location on any plane drawing of the underlying graph G . We then
 472 sketch ζ_c on $\pi(x_{D_1}, v)$. This is followed by sketching π_c , and then finally sketching the walk
 473 $\pi(v', x_{D_2})$. Since this sketch is over a path, we will refer to this walk in G as $\pi(\zeta_c)$.

474 ■ **Figure 7.** Left: a set of subwalks of cells in $resident(D)$. Right: the walks $\pi(\zeta_c)$ for each $c \in resident(D)$.

475 ► **Lemma 11.** For a given ball D in \mathcal{R} and two distinct cells c and c' in $resident(D)$, if
 476 $\pi(\zeta_c)$ and $\pi(\zeta_{c'})$ share a common vertex v , then e_c and $e_{c'}$ share a common endpoint D' .

477 **Proof.** Let $e_c = (D_1, D_2)$ and $e_{c'} = (D_3, D_4)$. For c (c'), the common vertex v must lie on a
 478 shortest path from either x_{D_1} or x_{D_2} (x_{D_3} or x_{D_4}) to v_c ($v_{c'}$) by construction. Without loss
 479 of generality, assume x_{D_1} and x_{D_3} . One of x_{D_1} or x_{D_3} must be at least as close as the other
 480 to v_c . Without loss of generality, assume x_{D_1} . By Lemma 8, this implies that D_1 contains
 481 $v_{c'}$, and is thus in $hit(v_{c'})$. We know that D is contained within $hit(v_{c'})$, as we only ever
 482 assign $base(v_{c'})$ to a member of $hit(v_{c'})$. Thus, in order for c' to be depth 3, D_1 must be
 483 either the same as D_3 or D_4 . Thus, e_c and $e_{c'}$ have a common endpoint. ◀

484 Lemma 11 implies that ζ_c and $\zeta_{c'}$ only cross if e_c and $e_{c'}$ share an endpoint. Since the
 485 only crossings occur between edges incident on the same vertex, G_D can be redrawn with
 486 these crossings removed. This immediately implies the following:

487 ► **Lemma 12.** G_D is a simple planar graph.

488 ► **Lemma 13.** There are $O(|\mathcal{R}|)$ cells of depth at most 3.

489 **Proof.** We first quickly argue that there is $O(n)$ cells of depth at most 2. By the definition
 490 of cell, there is at most n cells of depth 1, one for each ball in \mathcal{R} . By the existence of a
 491 planar dual support (Theorem 2) on \mathcal{R} with respect to all vertices of G , we know that for
 492 every cell of depth 2 corresponding to vertices v incident on balls R and R' , the connectivity
 493 of \mathcal{R}_v requires that R and R' share an edge. Since the dual support is planar, there is at
 494 most $3|\mathcal{R}| - 6$ such pairs, and thus at most $O(n)$ cells of depth 2.

495 For depth-3 cells, every edge of G_D corresponds to a resident depth-3 cell c of D , so
 496 $|resident(D)| \leq |E(G_D)|$. By Lemma 12, $|resident(D)| \leq 3|V(G_D)|$. By charging the depth-3
 497 cells to the total number of edges across all G_D for all $D \in \mathcal{R}$ using the planarity of G_D ,
 498 $|resident(D)| \leq 3|N_H(D)|$. Summing over all neighborhoods in the contracted Voronoi
 499 diagram of \mathcal{R} in G , we know the sum of degrees is at most $6|\mathcal{R}|$. Thus, $|Cell_3| \leq 18|\mathcal{R}|$. ◀

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687 **A** Missing proofs

688 **A.1** Weighted r -Dominating Set: Proof of Theorem 1

689 ► **Theorem 14.** *Given a set of balls \mathcal{R} in a planar graph G , a subset of vertices $U \subseteq V(G)$,*
 690 *and a weight function $w : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, an $O(1)$ approximation for the minimum weight coverage*
 691 *of U by balls of \mathcal{R} can be computed in polynomial time.*

692 **Proof.** Theorem 3 implies the balls in \mathcal{R} in G have $O(nk^3)$ shallow-cell complexity. Chan
 693 *et al.* [10] showed that for any set system with shallow cell complexity $O(n \text{ poly } k)$, an
 694 $O(1)$ -approximation for weighted set cover can be computed in polynomial time. ◀

695 Theorem 14 can now directly be applied to the r -dominating set problem.

696 **Proof of Theorem 1.** Consider the set of distance balls $\mathcal{R} = \{B(v, r) : v \in V_G\}$. If a vertex
 697 v' is within distance r of v , then v' is within the ball of $B(v, r) \in \mathcal{R}$. This implies that the
 698 set cover instance (V_G, \mathcal{R}) is exactly equivalent to r -dominating set in G . Therefore, if we
 699 apply the algorithm from Theorem 14 to (V_G, \mathcal{R}) , then we will get an $O(1)$ -approximation
 700 for r -dominating set in polynomial time. ◀

701 **B** Existence of Intersection Support

702 We now shift focus to a more general notion of support. For other more complicated
 703 applications, sometimes we need to work with set systems that have two different types of
 704 sets. We define an *intersection system* $(U, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$ as a set system where the elements are the
 705 sets of \mathcal{R} and the family of sets is \mathcal{B} , and we consider a set $R \in \mathcal{R}$ to be a “member” of

706 set $B \in \mathcal{B}$ if there is at least one element of U is in the intersection $R \cap B$. We define an
 707 *intersection support* to be a support graph of an intersection system $(U, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$. In other words,
 708 an *intersection support* is an undirected graph $H(\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$ where \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{B} are two families of
 709 subsets of some universe U and $H(\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$ is a graph on \mathcal{R} such that for every set $B \in \mathcal{B}$, all
 710 sets in \mathcal{R} that contain a common element with B form a connected subgraph of $H(\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$.

711 **Figure 8.** An intersection system with an intersection support. The red regions intersecting blue set B
 712 form a connected subgraph in the support.

713 Our notion of *intersection support* is equivalent to Raman and Ray’s notion of planar
 714 support for intersection hypergraphs [55], except we do not require that our support graphs
 715 be planar. In our case, we are looking at the situation where \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{B} are both sets of balls
 716 that lie in some underlying graph G . It is important to note that this is a generalization of
 717 both dual and primal support for the case of balls, since we can always consider the case
 718 where \mathcal{R} is a set of radius-0 balls on every vertex to get a primal support and the case where
 719 \mathcal{B} is the set of radius-0 balls on every vertex to get a dual support.

720 **Undirected case.** We reuse the same construction of G' , but in this case adding nodes
 721 for both \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{B} . It is easy to show that if G (and our augmentation G') is undirected,
 722 then the above trick of contracting the Voronoi partition with respect to \mathcal{R} works: Consider
 723 each \mathcal{R} node to be the center of a ball with radius $2r_{\max}$. If a ball R from \mathcal{R} and B from \mathcal{B}
 724 share a vertex in G , then the ball centered at x_R in G' of radius $2r_{\max}$ must contain x_B . By
 725 Lemma 4, we know that all $R' \in \mathcal{R}$ containing x_B must induce a connected subgraph in H ,
 726 satisfying the definition of intersection support.

727 In this section we show how to extend the technique to obtain an intersection support
 728 which also preserves forbidden minors even when G is directed.

729 **► Theorem 15 (Intersection Support).** *Any system of balls $(\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$ on an underlying graph G
 730 has an intersection support $H(\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$ such that if G does not contain a (contraction-)minor
 731 K with minimum vertex degree two, then neither does $H(\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$.*

732 B.1 Constructing an intersection support

733 To construct an intersection support for a directed graph G , we first construct G' , using
 734 $\mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{B}$ as our balls for the node set. This means that we create a node for each $D \in \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{B}$
 735 and delete all vertices that are not contained in any such D . We will additionally label
 736 each vertex (and node) with whether it is reachable from a ball in \mathcal{R} (*red*) or if it is *only*
 737 reachable from balls in \mathcal{B} (*blue*). Considering only the red vertices at first, we apply the
 738 same procedure of constructing the Voronoi partition with respect to \mathcal{R} and contracting
 739 each cell. We refer to this graph as H . H should now only contain blue vertices, blue nodes
 740 and red nodes. To define edge weights of H , we will say that edges between two red nodes
 741 have infinite weight, whereas all other edges inherit the minimum weight whenever two edges
 742 merge due to an edge contraction. From here, we flip the orientations of every edge in H ,

743 including those incident on nodes. We then construct a Voronoi partition with respect to the
 744 red nodes \mathcal{R} , and contract every cell, in this case yielding a graph H' only on the red nodes.

745 We first show that H' is a support graph, as was done with Lemma 4 for the dual system.

746 ► **Lemma 16.** *For every blue ball $B \in \mathcal{B}$ in a system of balls $(\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B})$ on an underlying*
 747 *graph G , the set of red balls $\mathcal{R}_B \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ that intersects B nontrivially must induce a connected*
 748 *subgraph in H' .*

749 **Proof.** Assume that $|\mathcal{R}_B| \geq 2$, as otherwise this holds trivially. Consider the closest red
 750 vertex u to B (smallest distance $d(x_B, u)$). By the construction of H , u was contracted into
 751 some red node $R \in \mathcal{R}$. In fact, $R \in \mathcal{R}_B$, $|\mathcal{R}_B| = 0$ by the definition of a red vertex. Since we
 752 always choose the minimum weight edge when merging, we know that x_B must be in the
 753 Voronoi cell of R in H . It suffices to show that the remaining $R' \in \mathcal{R}_B \setminus \{R\}$ must have a
 754 path to R within $H'[\mathcal{R}_B]$.

755 Consider a vertex v in $R' \cap B$, and the shortest paths $\pi(x_{R'}, v)$ and $\pi(x_B, v)$. We know
 756 that every vertex v' in $\pi(x_{R'}, v)$ must be in the G' Voronoi cell of R' . We claim that every
 757 vertex v' in $\pi(x_B, v)$ is either a red vertex in the G' Voronoi cell of a ball in \mathcal{R}_B or a blue
 758 vertex in the H Voronoi cell of a ball in \mathcal{R}_B . This lets us use the union of $\pi(x_{R'}, v)$ and $\pi(x_B, v)$
 759 to trace a path in H' from R' to R .

760 If v' is in $\pi(x_{R'}, v)$, then, by definition of shortest path, $d(x_B, v') \leq d(x_B, v)$ and thus v'
 761 is in B . With this in mind, we can split into cases based on whether v' is a red vertex or a
 762 blue vertex.

■ **Figure 9.** Left: a red vertex v' of $\pi(x_{R'}, v)$ must lie in the Voronoi cell of a red ball R' intersecting with B .
 Right: A blue vertex v' of $\pi(x_B, v)$ must lie in the H Voronoi cell of R' intersecting with B .

- 763 ■ If v' is red then v' must be in the Voronoi cell (in G') of some red ball R'' that contains
 764 v' . Since v' is also in B , this means that $R'' \cap B \neq \emptyset$, which implies that $R'' \in \mathcal{R}_B$.
 765 ■ If v' is blue, there must be some red vertex u' which is of the smallest distance, $d(v', u')$,
 766 among all red vertices. Since v is a red vertex, we know that $d(v', u') \leq d(v', v)$, hence:

$$767 \quad d(x_B, u') \leq d(x_B, v') + d(v', u') \leq d(x_B, v') + d(v', v) = d(x_B, v) \leq r_{\max}$$

768 This implies that u' must be in B .

769 Since u' is red, u' must be in some Voronoi cell of a red ball R'' (in G'). After the
 770 orientation flip and the construction of H , u' is contracted into $x_{R''}$, and thus $x_{R''}$ must
 771 be the closest red node to v' . This means v' is in the R'' Voronoi cell in H . Since
 772 $u' \in R'' \cap B$, $R'' \in \mathcal{R}_B$, thus every vertex in $\pi(x_B, v)$ is contracted into a red node which
 773 is in \mathcal{R}_B .

774 This means that we can simply perform a walk from R to R' in H' by going to the red
 775 ball corresponding to each vertex along $\pi(x_{R'}, v)$ and then backwards along $\pi(x_B, v)$. Thus,
 776 \mathcal{R}_B must form a connected subgraph in H' . ◀

777 **Proof of Theorem 15.** Construct H' described above as our intersection support. By Lemma
 778 16, we know that H' satisfies the definition of our intersection support, so it remains to show
 779 that H' contains no (contraction)-minor with minimum degree two that is not also a minor

780 of G . The construction of H' begins with the construction of a graph G' almost equivalent
781 to the one from Theorem 2, but for set system $(G, \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{B})$. From the proof of Theorem 2,
782 we know that this G' contains no minor K of minimum degree two. Since we only perform
783 contractions and vertex deletions after constructing G' , we know that H' is a minor of G' ,
784 and thus also contains no minor K . ◀

785 To conclude, any system of balls admit an intersection support which contains the same
786 forbidden minors as the underlying graph. Both the dual and intersection supports can be
787 computed in polynomial time. The primary bottleneck is the construction of the Voronoi
788 partitions, which Erwig [24] showed to be computable in $O(m + n \log n)$ time for graphs with
789 m edges and n vertices.